

Synthesis of Some New N^1 -Substituted-6-methyl-4-phenyl-quinolin-2(1*H*)-ones

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Quinolone (1) when N -alkylated with 2-chloropropionate in the presence of potassium carbonate gives 1-methoxycarbonyl-ethyl-6-methyl-4-phenylquinolin-2(1*H*)-one (2) which on treatment with hydrazine hydrate yields 1-hydrazidoethyl-6-dimethyl-4-phenylquinolin-2(1*H*)-one (3). Compound 3 reacts with various aldehydes to form arylidene derivatives (4). Cycloaddition of 4 with mercaptoacetic acid gives thiazolidinones (5). Further, the reaction of 3 with phenyl isothiocyanate yields N -substituted-thiocarbamate derivative (6) which when cyclised with NaOH furnishes the mercaptotriazole (7). The reaction of 3 with 3-acetyl-6-methylpyran-2,4-dione and ethyl chloroformate gives the heteroarylalkyl products 8 and 9 respectively.

Quinoline derivatives are drugs of therapeutic importance showing wide spectrum of biological activities. Although some work has been done on the synthesis and screening of some N^1 -substituted quinoline derivatives, it was con-

sidered worthwhile to incorporate heterocyclic moieties in the N^1 -position of 6-methyl-4-phenylquinolin-2(1*H*)-one (Scheme 1) to study the effect of N^1 -substitution on antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

All m.p.s. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on a Simadzu IR-470 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Purity of compounds in addition to the elemental analysis, was checked by tlc using silica gel G. All the compounds showed satisfactory microanalytical results for C, H and N.

Compound **1** was prepared by the reported method² by reacting *p*-toluidine with ethyl acetoacetate.

N¹-Methoxycarbonyl ethyl-6-methyl-4-phenylquinolin-2-(1H)-one (2) : A mixture of 6-methyl-4-phenylquinolin-2(1H)-one (**1**; 0.1 mol) and methyl 2-chloropropionate (0.1 mol) in dry acetone (50 ml) containing anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.5 g) was refluxed for 18 h on an oil-bath. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure to get a thick liquid, (5.25 g, 68%) (Found : C, 74.50; H, 5.70; N, 4.20. $C_{20}H_{19}NO_3$ requires : C, 74.74; H, 5.95; N, 4.35%); ν_{max} 1750 (ester C=O), 1650 cm^{-1} (cyclic C=O); δ 1.5 (3H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz, CH_3), 2.35 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 3.8 (3H, s, O- CH_3), 5.0 (1H, q, *J* 7.5 Hz, CH), 6.35 (1H, s, =CH), 6.9–7.5 (8H, m, ArH).

N¹-(2'-Propylhydrazido)-6-methyl-4-phenylquinolin-2(1H)-one (3) : A mixture of **2** (0.1 mol) and 80% hydrazine hydrate (0.1 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 3 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure to get solid which was crystallised from ethanol, (0.45 g, 79%), m.p. 176° (Found : C, 70.50; H, 5.80; N, 12.90. $C_{19}H_{19}N_3O_2$ requires : C, 71.00; H, 5.95; N, 13.07%); ν_{max} 3400, 3100 (NH), 1670 cm^{-1} (cyclic and acyclic C=O); δ 1.55 (3H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz, CH_3), 2.35 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 4.35 (2H, s br, NH_2), 4.95 (1H, q, *J* 7 Hz, CH), 6.75 (1H, s, =CH), 7.0–7.6 (8H, m, ArH), 9.45 (1H, s br, CONH).

N¹-(Arylidene propionamido)-6-methyl-4-phenylquinolin-2(1H)-ones (4a) : A mixture of **3** (0.001 mol) and aryl aldehyde (0.001 mol) in methanol (15 ml) containing acetic acid (1-2 drops) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 1.5 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure to get a solid which was crystallised from ethanol, (74 mg, 65%), m.p. 228° (Found : C, 65.05; H, 4.50; N, 8.55. $C_{26}H_{21}N_3O_2Cl_2$ requires : C, 65.13; H, 4.62; N, 8.76%); ν_{max} 3420, 3180 (NH), 1700–1660 (cyclic and acyclic C=O), 1610 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ 1.55 (3H, d, *J* 7 Hz, CH_3), 2.35 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 5.05 (1H, q, *J* 7.5 Hz, CH), 6.7 (1H, s, =CH), 6.9–8.2 (12H, m, ArH), 9.4 (1H, s, CONH).

Similarly, other compounds (yields 50–70%) were prepared; **4b**, m.p. 214°; **c**, 156°; **d**, 256°; **e**, 228°.

3-(6'-Methyl-4'-phenyl-2'-oxo-1'-propanamidyl)-4-aryl-1,3-thiazolidin-2(1H)-ones (5a) : A mixture of **4a** (0.001 mol) and mercaptoacetic acid (0.001 mol) with a pinch of anhydrous zinc chloride in DMF (10 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 6 h. The solid obtained was then crystallised

from DMF, (96 mg, 59%), m.p. >300° (Found : C, 64.40; H, 4.25; N, 8.01. $C_{28}H_{23}N_3O_3Cl_2$ requires : C, 64.62; H, 4.45; N, 8.07%); ν_{max} 3400–3200 (NH), 1710–1670 (C=O), 760 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); δ 1.5 (3H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz, CH_3), 2.35 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 3.2 (1H, s, CH-S), 3.7 (2H, s, S- CH_2), 4.95 (1H, q, *J* 7.5 Hz, CH), 6.75 (1H, s, =CH), 7.0–7.8 (11H, m, ArH), 9.45 (1H, s, CONH).

Similarly, other compounds (yields 55–70%) were prepared : **5b-e**, m.p.s. >300°.

4-Phenyl-1-(N¹-6'-methyl-4'-phenylquinolinopropionyl)-thiosemicarbazide (6) : A mixture of **3** (0.1 mol) and phenyl isothiocyanate (0.1 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 h on a steam-bath and the solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and cooled. The resulting solid was crystallized from ethanol, (75 mg, 61.4%), m.p. 90° (Found : C, 70.45; H, 5.31; N, 9.30. $C_{26}H_{24}N_3O_2S$ requires : C, 70.56; H, 5.46; N, 9.49%); ν_{max} 3200, 3050 (NH), 1690 (C=O), 1620 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ 1.5 (3H, d, *J* 7 Hz, CH_3), 2.3 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 4.5 (2H, s br, 2 × NH), 5.0 (1H, q, *J* 7 Hz, CH), 6.7 (1H, s, =CH), 6.9–7.8 (13H, m, ArH), 9.4 (1H, s, CONH).

1-Phenyl-2-[N¹-(6'-methyl-4'-phenylquinolin-2'(1H)-one-1'-yl)-5-mercapto-1,3,4-triazole (7) : Compound **6** (0.001 mol) was refluxed with 2 *N* NaOH (2 ml) for 3 h, then cooled, filtered and the filtrate was acidified with glacial acetic acid. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (72 mg, 61%), m.p. 151° (Found : C, 70.10; H, 5.00; N, 12.65. $C_{26}H_{22}N_4OS$ requires : C, 70.20; H, 5.05; N, 12.72%); ν_{max} 3500–3450 (SH), 1690 (C=O), 1615 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ 1.35 (3H, q, *J* 7 Hz, CH_3), 2.35 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 5.0 (1H, q, *J* 7 Hz, CH), 6.7 (1H, s, =CH), 6.9–7.8 (13H, m, ArH), 10.2 (1H, s, SH).

1-(6'-Methyl-4'-phenylquinolin-2'-one-1'-yl)propionyl-3,6-dimethylpyrano[3,4-b]pyrazole (8) : A mixture of **3** (0.001 mol), 3-acetyl-6-methylpyran-2,4-dione (0.001 mol) in methanol (15 ml) and acetic acid (2 drops) was refluxed for 4 h and concentrated. The separated solid was crystallized from methanol, (66 mg, 73%), m.p. 200° (Found : C, 70.60; H, 5.20; N, 9.38. $C_{26}H_{23}N_3O_4$ requires : C, 70.73; H, 5.25; N, 9.51%); δ 1.55 (3H, d, *J* 7 Hz, CH_3), 2.15 (3H, s, = CH_3), 2.35 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 2.4 (3H, s, another CH_3), 5.05 (1H, q, *J* 7 Hz, CH), 5.9 (1H, s, pyran =CH), 6.7 (1H, s, =CH), 6.9–7.8 (6H, m, ArH).

2-(6'-Methyl-4'-phenylquinolin-2'-one-1'-ylethyl)-5-chloro-1,3,4-oxadiazole (9) : A mixture of **3** (0.001 mol) and ethyl chloroformate (0.01 mol) in methanol (20 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 5 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the solid obtained was crystallized from ethanol, (66 mg, 65%), m.p. 232° (Found : C, 63.64; H, 4.36; N, 11.30. $C_{20}H_{16}N_3O_2Cl$ requires : C, 65.66; H, 4.4; N, 11.48%); ν_{max} 1690 (C=O), 1620 (C=N), 1050 (C-O-C), 760 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); δ 1.55 (3H, d, *J* 7 Hz, CH_3), 2.3 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 6.7 (1H, s, =CH), 7.0–7.8 (8H, m, ArH).

NOTE

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